

THE EFFECT OF LAVENDER AROMATHERAPY ON INSOMNIA IN CLASS XI ADOLESCENTS AT SMAN 01 TAJURHALANG BOGOR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

In adolescents, insomnia is often influenced by factors such as poor habits and stress. Lavender aromatherapy has been identified as a potential therapy to improve sleep quality. This study aims to examine the effect of lavender aromatherapy on insomnia in adolescents in grade XI at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang. The research objectives are to determine the effect of lavender aromatherapy on insomnia, as well as identify age, gender, and level of insomnia before and after the intervention in adolescents. The research method used was a quantitative quasi-experimental pre-test post-test design. Data were collected through measurement of insomnia before and after lavender aromatherapy, with a sample of 60 adolescents. Statistical tests used Wilcoxon. The results showed that more than half of the respondents were 17 years old, with the majority being female. Before the intervention, most respondents experienced mild insomnia. After lavender aromatherapy, there was a significant improvement in sleep quality, with more than half of the respondents no longer experiencing insomnia. The Wilcoxon results showed a $p=0.001 < 0.005$ value, indicating a significant difference between insomnia conditions before and after the intervention. The conclusion in this study is the provision of lavender aromatherapy proved effective in reducing the degree of insomnia in adolescents in grade XI at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang. The results of this study support the use of lavender aromatherapy as an intervention to improve sleep quality in adolescents who experience insomnia.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescents, according to WHO (2018), cover the age range of 10-19 years, while the National Population and Family Planning Board (BKKBN) (2019) extends the definition of adolescents up to the age of 24 years, as long as they are unmarried. In Indonesia, there are approximately 66.8 million adolescents aged 10-24 years (BPS, 2021). Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood, during which they face various demands and challenges from the expanding environment, such as school, community, and places of worship. The busy activities make adequate and quality sleep very important for their health and well-being (Tarwoto, 2012). Sleep disorders, such as insomnia, can have a significant impact on the daily life of adolescents, causing them to be less productive, have difficulty concentrating, and become easily angered. A survey from the National Sleep Foundation in the United States shows that people with sleep difficulties often

experience a decline in their ability to complete tasks and problems in memory and learning (Rafknowledge, 2018).

Insomnia in adolescents ranges from 11-24% globally, but in some countries this figure can reach 50-60%. In the United States, around 76% of adolescents are reported to experience insomnia (Alison Deshong, 2024). In Indonesia, the prevalence of insomnia reaches 67%, with 55.8% experiencing mild insomnia and 23.3% moderate insomnia (Fernando & Hidayat, 2020). Poor sleep habits, such as snoring and lack of sleep duration, are also often found in adolescents (Candra, 2018). To overcome insomnia, there are two main approaches: pharmacological and non-pharmacological. Pharmacological therapy involves the use of medications such as benzodiazepines and non-benzodiazepines. On the other hand, non-pharmacological therapies, such as the use of aromatherapy, are becoming increasingly popular. Aromatherapy, particularly lavender, is known for its relaxing effects. Lavender essential oil, derived from the *Lavandula angustifolia* plant, contains linalool acetate, which helps relax the nerves and muscles, and increases the frequency of alpha waves in the brain, which can reduce sleep disturbances or insomnia.

Lavender aromatherapy is also safe to use and rarely causes allergies, making it a good choice to improve sleep quality (Firliansyah et al., 2021; Ramadhian & Zettira, 2017). Based on the preliminary observation study conducted by the researcher on Insomnia in 15 students of class XI IPA 2 at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang using the standard Insomnia Rating Scale (KSPBJ-IRS) questionnaire method via googleform, the results showed that all 15 students have insomnia. The reason they have difficulty sleeping is that most of the students' minds are filled with various matters, making it difficult for them to relax and causing them to feel sleepy during the day. This factor can result in difficulty concentrating during lessons, leading to a decline in both academic and non-academic achievements.

2. METHOD

This study used a quantitative research type. The type of research used was a quasi pre-experimental with a one group pre-test post-test approach. This research was conducted at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang, Bogor Regency. This research was conducted in July 2024. The population of this research was 155 teenage students from 10 class XI SMAN 01 TAJURHALANG who had insomnia. Sampling in this study used a Non-probability Sampling technique with a Purposive Sampling method. The total sample in this study was 60 respondents. This study used bivariate analysis, namely the Wilcoxon test to see the relationship between the dependent and independent variables, with a significance level of 0.05. Through the Wilcoxon statistical test, the P-value will be obtained, where in this study a significance level of 0.05 is used. Research between two variables is said to be related if it has a p-value ≤ 0.05 and is said to be unrelated if $p > 0.05$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Distribution of General Characteristics of Respondents with Insomnia in Grade XI at SMAN 1 Tajurhalang, Bogor Regency. (n=60)

No	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	16	15	25
2	17	39	65
3	18	6	10
Total		60	100

According to Table 1, the age distribution of insomnia among grade XI students of SMAN 1 Tajurhalang shows that more than half of the respondents are 17 years old (65%), a small portion are 16 years old (25%), and 10% are 18 years old. This research is in line and consistent with the research conducted by Firliansyah et al. (2021) with the majority of respondents aged 15-18 years. 18 teenagers (52.9%) were 17 years old and 9

teenagers (26.5%) were 18 years old. The results of this study are consistent with the existing theory where changes in the circadian rhythm in adolescents shift their sleep time to a later time.

A study by Crowley et al. (2018) confirms that adolescents experience a significant "phase delay", which makes them sleep and wake up later compared to children and adults. The results of this study are also supported by research conducted by Firotika et al. (2023) with the majority of respondents aged 14-17 years. There were 8 adolescents (47%) at the age of 17 years. This study supports the theory that age and biological, psychosocial, cognitive, and environmental development play an important role in influencing insomnia in adolescents. It is currently often found that adolescents experience sleep disturbances due to the habit of opening social media and playing online games, causing them to experience insomnia (Anggraini & Ratnawati, 2022). Sleep can be something difficult to achieve, and this difficult sleeping condition is known as Insomnia (Anggraini & Ratnawati, 2022). Based on the data above, the researcher assumes that adolescents at the productive age of 17 years are easily experiencing insomnia due to biological development, lifestyle, environmental factors causing disrupted sleep, and poor sleep quality.

Table 2 Gender Distribution of Adolescent Insomnia Students in Grade XI at SMAN 1 Tajurhalang. (n=60)

No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Man	25	41,67
2	Woman	35	51,33
Total		60	100

Based on the frequency distribution table of gender characteristics among adolescent insomnia students in grade XI of SMAN 1 Tajurhalang, it shows that more than half of the female adolescent respondents, namely 35 people, with a percentage of (58.33%) and nearly half of the male respondents, 25 people, with a percentage of (41.67%).

This research is consistent and in line with the research conducted by Anggraini & Ratnawati (2022), which showed that 30 female respondents (71.4%), while 12 male respondents (28.6%). This research is also supported by theory. In women, hormonal changes during the menstrual cycle, pregnancy, and menopause can affect sleep patterns. Estrogen and progesterone are known to have an effect on sleep quality. A study by Baker & Driver (2007) showed that hormonal fluctuations can cause sleep disturbances in adolescent girls. Gender is closely related to insomnia, consistent with the results of a study by Zhang et al. (2016), which stated that women are more likely to experience insomnia compared to men, which is related to puberty where ovarian hormones during the menstrual cycle cause emotional instability. Estrogen levels will decrease as menstruation approaches, and this will cause sleep disturbances in women. Based on the data above, the researcher assumes that the female gender is very influential when entering adolescence, where the estrogen hormone before menstruation and poor coping strategies are what make women more susceptible to insomnia compared to men.

Table 3 Insomnia Measurement Results Among Grade XI Students Table 5.3 Insomnia Measurement Results Among Grade XI Students

No	Insomnia	Frequency	Percentage
1	No insomnia	0	0
2	Mild insomnia	46	76,67
3	Severe insomnia	14	23,33
4	Very severe insomnia	0	0
Total		60	100

According to the frequency distribution of pretest/before Lavender aromatherapy Insomnia in table 3, the results from 60 respondents are: none of the adolescents (0%) had no insomnia, the majority of adolescents had

mild insomnia 46 (76.67%), a small portion of adolescents had severe insomnia 14 (23.33%) and no adolescent had very severe Insomnia (0%).

This research was supported by the Insomnia theory, which is characterized by disturbances in the amount, quality or timing of sleep in an individual. Sleep disturbances can interfere with physical, emotional, cognitive, and social development. These research findings are consistent with the research conducted by Anisya et al. (2023) before the lavender aromatherapy was given, with 11 respondents (39.3%) having poor sleep quality and 17 respondents (60.7%) having moderate sleep quality. The research findings are also consistent with the research conducted by Firotika et al. (2023) before the lavender aromatherapy was given, with 5 people (29%) having severe insomnia and 12 people (71%) having mild insomnia. The total sample used in the study was 17 respondents. Based on the above data, the researchers assume that during this time, adolescents experience a spectrum of mild to severe insomnia symptoms and impacts on daily life. It is important to recognize that insomnia is a complex condition.

Table 4 Insomnia Measurement Results for Grade XI Students at SMAN 1 Tajurhalang Posttest/After Lavender Aromatherapy

No	Insomnia	Frequency	Percentage
1	No insomnia	43	71,67
2	Mild insomnia	17	28,33
3	Severe insomnia	0	0
4	Very severe insomnia	0	0
Total		60	100

Based on the frequency distribution of posttest/after administration of lavender aromatherapy in adolescent respondents in table 4, the results obtained from 60 respondents were that more than half of the adolescent respondents, namely 43 adolescents (71.67%), did not have insomnia. Nearly half of the adolescent respondents after being given lavender aromatherapy had results of adolescents who originally experienced severe insomnia becoming mild insomnia, as many as 17 (28.33%), adolescents who had severe insomnia were none or 0 (0%) and adolescents had very severe insomnia none (0%).

This research result is in accordance with and aligned with the research conducted by Aryani (2019) after being given lavender aromatherapy, with the initial result of experiencing a mild degree of insomnia, now more than half of the respondents becoming non-insomnia (67%). These results support the theory about the relaxation effect, influence on neurotransmitters, decreased cortisol, and improved sleep quality from lavender aromatherapy. A study by Ozkaraman et al. (2018) found that the use of lavender aromatherapy in adolescents with insomnia had a positive effect on their sleep quality. Adolescents exposed to lavender scent reported falling asleep faster and sleeping more soundly.11 Based on the above data, the researcher assumes that lavender aromatherapy can be an effective and safe method in reducing insomnia and improving sleep quality in adolescents, as indicated by the reduction of severe insomnia to mild insomnia in 17 (28.33%) adolescents.

Table 5 The Effect of Lavender Aromatherapy on Insomnia in Class XI Students of SMAN 1 Tajurhalang. (n=60)

Kolmogorov-Smirnov				
	Statistic	Df	Sig	Statistic
Pre-Test	0,116	60	0,042	0,947
Post-Test	0,196	60	0,001	0,948

This test showed that the Lavender Aromatherapy variables before and after the administration of lavender aromatherapy based on the significant value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test met the parameters <0.05 . This

indicates that the data was not normally distributed, so the researcher used the Wilcoxon Test to determine the effect.

Table 6 The Effect of Lavender Aromatherapy on Insomnia in Grade XI Students of SMAN 1 Tajurhalang. (n=60)

Pre Test - Post Test	
Z	-6,230 ^b
P-value	0,001

Based on the frequency distribution table 6 above, the statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test shows that the decrease in adolescent insomnia in this study has a p-value = 0.001 < α = 0.005, which means that H_a is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the administration of lavender aromatherapy for insomnia in class XI adolescents between the pretest and posttest. Thus, the results show that the administration of lavender aromatherapy for insomnia has an effect on reducing the degree of insomnia in class XI students of SMAN 01 Tajurhalang.

This study found a decrease in the degree of insomnia in grade XI students at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang after being given lavender aromatherapy. Based on the analysis results, the descriptive statistical summary of the two samples or pretest and posttest data is shown. Based on the results of the Wilcoxon test in table 5.6, it can be concluded that the decrease in adolescent insomnia in this study had a p-value of 0.001 < α = 0.005, which means that H_a is accepted, so it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the administration of lavender aromatherapy for insomnia in grade XI students between the pretest and posttest. So from these results, it can be concluded that the administration of lavender aromatherapy for insomnia has an effect on reducing the degree of insomnia in grade XI students at Sman 1 Tajurhalang.

This research is supported by Firotika et al. (2023). The analytical test of this study used a paired sample t-test. The results showed that there was an effect of lavender aromatherapy on the incidence of insomnia in young women with a p-value = 0.001 (α < 0.005). This is supported by the existing theory that lavender essential oil contains linalool and linalyl acetate compounds that have a relaxing effect on the central nervous system. Lavender aromatherapy works by stimulating the brain's nervous system, which plays a role in regulating emotions, thereby producing a calming effect and reducing anxiety that often disturbs sleep.

The use of lavender essential oil as a therapy has been proven to improve sleep quality and reduce sleep disturbances through the influence of its aroma on the nervous system and mental well-being. A study conducted by the National Institute for Environmental Studies in Japan explains that the linalool content in lavender oil has an anti-anxiety effect. This finding supports the use of lavender aromatherapy oil as a highly effective traditional medicine for insomnia. Based on the data and research results above, the researcher can assume that lavender can improve sleep quality, especially for adolescents. This is evidenced by the very significant results of the pretest and posttest. Lavender aromatherapy can also help reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety in adolescents, which are often a contributing factor to insomnia. In addition, lavender aromatherapy is more readily available and relatively inexpensive, and has many benefits.

4. CONCLUSION

- Identified characteristics of respondents insomnia teenagers in grade XI of SMAN 01 Tajurhalang. Where the research results more than half of the respondents aged 17 years (65%). Based on sex characteristics where the majority of respondents are Female, namely, more than half of the respondents 35 female teenagers with a percentage (58.33%).
- Identified insomnia measurement results on high school students in grade XI at SMAN 1 Tajurhalang pre-test/before given Lavender Aromatherapy, the majority of teenagers have mild insomnia, as many as 46 (76.67%), a small portion of teenagers who have severe insomnia 14 (23.33%).

- c. Identified insomnia measurement results on high school students in grade XI at SMAN 1 Tajurhalang post-test/after given Lavender Aromatherapy, teenagers who do not have insomnia more than half of the respondents, namely as many as 43 teenagers (71.67%).
- d. Analyzed the research results that have been done that there is an Effect of Giving Lavender Aromatherapy On Insomnia in Class XI Students at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang, Bogor Regency marked by a p-value of $0.001 < 0.005$. So H_a is accepted, which means There is an Effect of Giving Lavender Aromatherapy On Insomnia in Class XI Students at SMAN 01 Tajurhalang, Bogor Regency.

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